

Fermat Numbers and Representation Based on Digit Count

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In this study, a closed form of Fermat numbers expressed through the number of digits is defined.

Definitions ;

$F(n)$ = Fermat number

$d(Fn)$ = Number of digits = m

$k = 2^n$

Proposition ;

A Fermat number can be written in terms of the digit count m as follows:

$$F(n) = (2^{(k-m)} \cdot 10^m + 5^m) / 5^m$$

Proof ;

$$(2^{(k-m)} \cdot 10^m + 5^m) = (2^k)(5^m) + 5^m$$

$$(2^k)(5^m) + 5^m = 5^m(2^k + 1)$$

$$5^m(2^k + 1) / 5^m = 2^k + 1$$

$$2^k + 1 = 2^{(2^n)} + 1$$

$$2^{(2^n)} + 1 = F(n)$$

Explanation ;

The above expression is an algebraic transformation and does not present a new mathematical result. It is presented here since such a representation based on digit count has not been encountered in the literature.28/09/2025

Ender UYGUN

enderport@gmail.com

ÇANAKKALE